

DEPOSITION OF FIBERS OF DIFFERENT OXIDES ON GLASS SUBSTRATES FOR THE PHOTOCATALYTIC PRODUCTION OF HYDROGEN

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7410820

Luana Goes Soares

Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul – Laboratory of Ceramic Materials

Annelise Kopp Alves

Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul – Laboratory of Ceramic Materials

ABSTRACT

The photocatalytic production of hydrogen has been considered a promising option to obtain energy in an environmentally sustainable way. Porous and crystalline semiconductors are often used as photocatalysts in hydrogen production. In this work, we report the deposition of TiO_2 and TiO_2 fibers containing two different tungsten precursors (H_2WO_4 or $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), which are heat treated between 650°C and 800°C , on glass substrates, which will be used as photocatalysts in the production of hydrogen when irradiated by ultraviolet (UV) light. All samples were characterized by: X-ray diffraction (XRD) to identify the crystalline phases formed, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) for microstructural analysis of the surface of the films and by colorimetry. The results showed that all samples were effective in the production of hydrogen, especially the films containing $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ fibers treated at a temperature of 800°C . The presence of tungsten in the fibers favored the formation of hydroxyl radicals (OH) and adsorption sites on the surface of the samples. This facilitated the transfer of electrons between the two photocatalysts (TiO_2 and WO_3), contributing to a high rate of photocatalytic hydrogen production.

Keywords: Energy; fibers; Films; Hydrogen.

1. INTRODUCTION

Several materials have been tested to function as a substrate, including: glass, granular activated carbon, stainless steel, quartz, ceramic materials, zeolites, polymers, among others (SILVA, 2018).

Glasses are used as an excellent host material, due to their excellent thermal, optical, photocatalytic properties, chemical stability and ease of production (SILVA, 2018).

Several methods have been employed in the deposition of thin films on ceramic substrates; such as: chemical vapor deposition, *magnetron sputtering* ; *dip coating*, and *spin coating* among others. For thick films, the most used application techniques are flat screen printing, airbrushing, incavography and digital printing. The latter associated with heat treatment (SILVA, 2018).

In photocatalytic processes, the supports used in immobilization need to combine high porosity and adsorption capacity, aiming to provide an increase in surface area, greater thermal stability during crystalline phase changes, and a reduction in photocatalyst density, allowing greater interaction photocatalyst/pollutant (SILVA, 2018).

In the case of using glass as a substrate, the photocatalytic properties of the films will depend mainly on the method used in the synthesis of the samples. Both thin and thick films can be obtained. As occurs when using other materials, the greater the thickness, the greater the number of crystals, the greater the number of electron/hole pairs, which consequently makes the photocatalysis more effective. Thus, for the success of the photocatalytic reaction, it is essential to analyze the composition of the substrate (SILVA, 2018).

spin-coating technique was used for the deposition of thin films of TiO_2 , TiO_2/WO_3 and $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on glass substrates, and its photocatalytic efficiency for the hydrogen generation was evaluated.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The reagents chosen for sample preparation. Titanium propoxide (Sigma-Aldrich) contains the titanium ion essential for the formation of titanium oxide. Glacial acetic acid (Sigma-Aldrich) was used to accelerate the hydrolysis reaction of titanium propoxide. Anhydrous ethyl alcohol (Zeppelin) which was used as the general solvent of the solution. A 10 wt% solution of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP – Sigma-Aldrich, 1,300,000 g/mol) was used as a polymeric vehicle for producing the fibers by *electrospinning* . Tungstic acid (Sigma-Aldrich) was used as a tungsten precursor. Hydrogen peroxide (Dinâmica) was used as an oxidizing agent.

2.1 Electrospinning

For the synthesis of fibers by *electrospinning* , 3 types of precursor solutions were prepared. The TiO_2 solution contained a mixture of 2.5 mL of titanium propoxide (TiP); 2 mL of glacial acetic acid and 5 mL of an alcoholic solution containing 10% by weight of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP). The TiO_2/WO_3 solution contained the titanium solution mixture

described above plus 1 mL of hydrogen peroxide and 0.10 g of H_2WO_4 , which were kept under magnetic stirring for 15 minutes. The $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution was obtained by mixing the initial solution containing titanium, adding 1 mL of hydrogen peroxide and 0.10 g of $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which were kept under magnetic stirring for 15 minutes.

The fibers were produced by filling a 5 mL plastic syringe, connected to a stainless steel hypodermic needle, with an internal diameter of 1 mm, with the precursor solution. The needle was connected to the high voltage source. The distance between the tip of the needle and the rotating cylindrical collector coated with aluminum foil was 12 cm. A voltage of 13.5 kV was applied between the needle and the collector. An infusion pump (KD Scientific) controlled the flow of the precursor solution (1.8 mL/h). The fibers were collected every 30 minutes, for a period of 4 hours daily, for each formulation.

2.1.1 – Heat treatment

The fibers obtained were subjected to a thermal treatment in an electric oven (Sanchis) at temperatures of 650 °C, 700 °C, 750 °C and 800 °C, with a 1 hour hold and a heating rate of 1.4 °C/min, in order to remove the polymeric material and form crystalline phases. Figure 1 shows the appearance of TiO_2 fibers obtained by *electrospinning*.

Figure 1 - Photographic image of TiO_2 fibers obtained by *electrospinning*, after heat treatment

2.1.2 Spin-coating

Before deposition of the solutions on the glass plates, they were washed with a solution of acetone and water at 80% v/v. After the glass plates were washed, they were placed in an ultrasonic bath for 15 minutes and then dried with absorbent paper. To prepare solutions of the

fibers and the P25 standard, 0.25 g of the TiO₂-P25 standard (commercial Evonik-powder) or of the thermally treated fibers at 650 °C, 700 °C, 750 °C and 800 °C were mixed in 8 mL of anhydrous ethanol and 0.8 mL of acetylacetone (Sigma-Aldrich). The mixtures were dispersed in an ultrasound for 10 minutes. After this period, 0.1 mL of Triton X-100 (Sigma-Aldrich) and 0.4 g of polyvinylbityral (PVB) were added and kept under magnetic stirring for 10 minutes.

The films were obtained by deposition of 5 drops of each of the previously prepared solutions on glass plates (1 cm x 2 cm) covered with FTO (*Fluorine-Doped Tin Oxide* , XOP Glass). These glass plates were fixed with double-sided tape in the appropriate place on the equipment to start the *spin-coating process* . The equipment used was a (TC 100 Spin Coater) with a rotation of 800 RPM for 30 s.

2.1.3 Characterization

A scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL JSM 6060) was used to analyze the morphology of the samples. This equipment was equipped with EDS (dispersive energy spectroscopy), which helped to identify the Ti, O and W, Na, (OH) atoms present in the samples, according to their composition. The X-ray diffraction was determined by a diffractometer (PHILIPS, X'PERT) with CuK α radiation, operating with a voltage of 40 kV and current of 40 mA, speed of 0.05°/min and step of 1 s in a range of 5 to 75°. The diffractograms obtained were compared to the JCPDS database (*Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards*) using the X'Pert HighScore® *software to determine the present phases*. The Kubelka and Munk correlation was used to provide the bandgap energy values of the synthesized films and the TiO₂-P25 standard (commercial Evonik-powder). A UV-Vis-NIR dual-beam spectrophotometer (Cary 5000), with an integrating sphere in diffuse light reflection mode, was used in determining the measurements. Colorimetry was analyzed by a Konica-Minolta spectrophotometer, CM 2600d, with integrated sphere and ultraviolet filter. The illuminant used was D65, and color measurements were obtained based on an observer at 10° away.

2.1.4 Production of hydrogen by *water-splitting*

For the photocatalytic production of hydrogen, a quartz reactor consisting of double walls was used, through which water circulated, with a constant temperature of 25 °C. Then, the catalysts (films), one at a time, were immobilized in a solution of 7.5 mL of deionized water and 2.5 mL of ethanol. Prior to the start of irradiation, analytical argon was bubbled through to remove dissolved gases and the system was deaerated through a vacuum line. A 300 W xenon lamp illuminated the reactor to simulate sunlight. The gases produced were collected using a Hamilton gas syringe at intervals of 30 min for 4 h and quantified using a GC-Agilent 6820

chromatograph. The total volume of samples injected into the chromatograph was 1,000 μL (SOARES, 2021).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the surface of TiO_2 (2a-b), TiO_2/WO_3 (2c) and $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2d). Analyzing these images, the fibers do not seem to have a preferred orientation, appearing to have an elongated and continuous microstructure. The fibers that make up the TiO_2 , TiO_2/WO_3 and $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ films shown mainly in Figure 2a-c seem to be made up of a set of agglomerated and interconnected particles. These agglomerates occur because the fibers have in their structure several grains, with larger sizes. Energy dispersive scattering spectroscopy (EDS), Figure 3, identified and confirmed the presence of Na, (OH), oxygen, titanium and tungsten atoms in different regions of the sample, depending on the film composition.

Figure 2 - SEM images of TiO_2 (ab), TiO_2/WO_3 (c) and $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (d) films

Figure 3 - SEM EDS images of (a) TiO_2 , (b) TiO_2/WO_3 and (c) $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ films

Figure 4 presents the phases identified by X-ray diffraction of TiO_2 , TiO_2/WO_3 and $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, with thermal treatment at 650 °C, 700 °C, 750 °C and 800 °C, respectively. Figure 5 shows that samples without heat treatment (STT) are amorphous, that is, without shape. As the films containing the fibers without heat treatment (STT) were amorphous for both formulations, as shown in Figure 4, we have only included a graph for illustration purposes.

Figure 4 - Diffractograma of STT samples

For the TiO_2 samples, Figure 5a, it was observed that up to the temperature of 700 °C, only the anatase crystalline phase (JCPDS 01-078-2486), with the first characteristic peak at $2\Theta = 25.271^\circ$, was detected. The samples containing fibers treated from 750 °C formed, in addition to the anatase phase, the rutile phase (JCPDS 01-077-0442). The first characteristic peak of the rutile phase appears at approximately $2\Theta = 27.294^\circ$. The rutile phase appears, due to the increase in the calcination temperature, which causes a transition from the anatase

crystalline phase to rutile. For the TiO_2/WO_3 samples, Figure 5b, treated at a temperature of 650 °C, the anatase and brookite phases were identified (JCPDS 01-075-1582) for TiO_2 , the latter with first characteristic peak, at $2\Theta = 25.425^\circ$. Fibers treated from 700 °C showed a rutile phase for TiO_2 in addition to the anatase and brookite phases (JCPDS 01-077-0442), the latter with the first characteristic peak at $2\Theta = 27.294^\circ$. For WO_3 , the monoclinic phase was detected (JCPDS 00-032-1393), with the first characteristic peak at approximately $2\Theta = 23^\circ$, identified in all samples of this formulation, treated between 650 °C and 800 °C. As for the $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ samples treated at a temperature of 700 °C, Figure 5c, the monoclinic phase was detected for WO_3 , the anatase and brookite phase for TiO_2 . For fibers calcined at 750 °C, the anatase and brookite phases were identified for TiO_2 and tetragonal (JCPDS 00-002-0414) for WO_3 , with the first peak at $2\Theta = 37.604^\circ$. The fibers calcined at 800 °C showed anatase, brookite and rutile phases (JCPDS 01-077-0442) for TiO_2 and predominance of the tetragonal phase for WO_3 . The $\text{Na}(\text{OH})$ group presented the orthorhombic phase (JCPDS 00-035-1009) identified in all samples treated between 650 °C and 800 °C, with the first peak at approximately $2\Theta = 16^\circ$.

Figure 5 – Diffractogram of samples of (a) TiO_2 , (b) TiO_2/WO_3 and of (c) $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

The records for each sample were obtained based on the CIE-L*a*b* system, and the measurement range covered the entire visible spectrum (400 to 700 nm). Thus, during the colorimetric tests, the P25 standard and the TiO_2 samples had maximum absorbance in the dark blue color region, influenced by positive a^* values (red color) and negative b^* values (blue color). The dark hue of the samples was determined based on negative ΔL^* values. The TiO_2/WO_3 and $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ samples had maximum absorbance in the light blue color region, influence of negative a^* values (green color) and negative b^* values (green color). blue). The light hue of the samples was determined based on positive ΔL^* values. The maximum absorbance in the blue color region reached by TiO_2 , TiO_2/WO_3 and $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ samples was already expected, since both precursor solutions are yellow in color, differing

only in hue. And, in colorimetric analyzes, the maximum absorbance occurs in the complementary color region and, in this case, the complementary color to yellow is blue. Both the P25 standard and the TiO_2 and TiO_2/WO_3 and $TiO_2/Na_2WO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ samples had a good amount of perceived light, according to the brightness values (%L).

Figure 6 shows, in terms of values, how much hydrogen each sample produced. The TiO_2 , TiO_2/WO_3 and $TiO_2/Na_2WO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ catalysts that showed the best photocatalytic performance for hydrogen production: 72%, 95% and 96%, respectively. These samples were synthesized at 800 °C and presented specific surface areas of 9.8, 28.5 and 30.9 m^2/g , respectively. The higher specific surface area can also explain the fact that the $TiO_2/Na_2WO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ sample heat-treated at 800 °C was the most photoactive during hydrogen production, in addition to the presence of oxygen and Na^+ ions, which also contributed to the increase of hydroxyl groups (OH) on the surface of the material (MUCCILLO, 2008). (EL-YAZEED, 2019), report in their study the synthesis of mesoporous WO_3/TiO_2 photocatalysts, with different weight loads of WO_3 , which were used in the removal of an aqueous solution of methylene blue. The FTIR results showed that the OH groups bound more easily to the surface of the 10% by weight WO_3/TiO_2 sample, which influenced the increase in its photodegradation capacity in the UV-visible region.

Figure 6 – Production of hydrogen by *water-splitting*

Table 1 - Evolution of hydrogen production using films synthesized by *spin-coating* as photocatalysts

Films	H ₂ production
TiO ₂ -650°C	38%
TiO ₂ -700 °C	43%
TiO ₂ -750 °C	44%
TiO ₂ -800 °C	72%
TiO ₂ /WO ₃ -650 °C	74%
TiO ₂ /WO ₃ -700 °C	76%
TiO ₂ /WO ₃ -750 °C	78%
TiO ₂ /WO ₃ -800 °C	95%
TiO ₂ /Na ₂ WO ₄ .2H ₂ O- 650 °C	91%
TiO ₂ /Na ₂ WO ₄ .2H ₂ O- 700 °C	87%
TiO ₂ /Na ₂ WO ₄ .2H ₂ O- 750 °C	90%
TiO ₂ /Na ₂ WO ₄ .2H ₂ O- 800 °C	96%
P25	23%

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

EL-YAZEED, A.; AHMED, A. "Photocatalytic activity of mesoporous WO₃/TiO₂ nanocomposites for the photodegradation of methylene blue", 2019.

MUCCILLO, E. "Oxygen ion conductors - a brief review", 2008.

SILVA, L. " Correlation between photochromic properties and photocatalytic activity of titanium and tungsten oxides", 2018.

SOARES, L.; VAZ, M.; TEIXEIRA, S.; ALVES, A. "Absorbance determination and photocatalytic production of hydrogen using tungsten and TiO₂ oxide nanostructures as catalyst", 2021.